

**CONSTITUENTS OF THE SEEDS OF *BLEPHARIS EDULIS*,
PERS. PART II. THE COMPOSITION OF THE
OIL. (A CORRECTION).**

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The formula, $C_{37}H_{47}O, 2H_2O$, was erroneously ascribed to the sterol described in the above communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 18, 365). The correct formula appears to be $C_{37}H_{42}O_2$. (Found in air-dried samples: C, 78.01, 78.04; H, 10.34, 10.30. $C_{37}H_{42}O_2$ requires C, 78.26; H, 10.15 per cent).

The following data should be inserted at the beginning of page 366.

TABLE VIII.

Percentage of Saturated Acids in the Oil.

Acid.	Found in the saturated acid fraction.	Found in the total fatty acids.	Found in the original oil.
Palmitic	43.44%	5.38%	4.93%
Stearic	54.72	6.77	6.20
Arachidic	0.134	0.017	0.015
Unsaturated	1.544	0.191	0.175

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Received July 28, 1938.

